

RESEARCH ON SKH51+WC+B83 COMPOSITE GRADIENT COATING BY ESD METHOD**Xin Du,***postgraduate student**Sumy National Agrarian University**Xinxiang University**ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1996-602X***Tarelnyk V.,***Doctor of science, professor**Sumy National Agrarian University**ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2005-5861***Konoplianchenko Ie.***PhD, associate professor**Sumy National Agrarian University**ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4814-1796***ABSTRACT**

With the development of the electro-spark deposition (ESD) process, researchers have conducted a lot of studies on single-coated materials. On the base of researches, people began to conduct research on composite coatings to meet the multiple functional requirements. This article mainly studied the composite coating SKH51+WC+B83, and studied the surface characteristics of each deposited layer. Composite coatings can improve the wear resistance, corrosion resistance, and reduce friction of the coating. Composite coating can increase coating thickness and extends coating service life. Composite coating outer coating mainly selected wear-resistant materials which included metal ceramics, intermetallic compounds and high entropy alloys. The intermediate layer was mainly nickel material, which plays the role of connecting the wear-resistant layer. This research used the idea of gradient structure to select the iron alloy material SKH51, which had good adhesion, wear resistance and impact toughness, and plays the role of transition coating. The WC-10Co deposition material was used to further improve the wear resistance of the coating. Babbitt B83 material was used for deposition to further reduce the friction of the coating to achieve the anti-friction function. It has better corrosion resistance than WC coating. The composite coating SKH51+WC+B83 has good properties, which can meet the requirements of remanufacturing engineering for super-life surface, upgrade the coating performance, and make the mechanical parts perform better than the original surface.

Keywords: composite coating, gradient structure, transition coating, SKH51, WC, tribological properties, toughness.

1 Introduction

Coatings can improve the surface properties of metal materials. Due to process limitations, the thickness of the deposited coating cannot be too thick. One-layer coating that is too thick will result in increased surface defects in the coating. Composite coatings can avoid the problems of one-layer coating. It can increase the overall coating thickness, improve surface performance and lifespan. The functional requirements of coating surfaces have changed from single function to multiple functions [1, 2]. Composite coatings can meet a variety of coating performance requirements. Especially, it can meet the special needs of enterprises for ultra-long life parts and wear resistance. It can save companies a lot of maintenance funds. Composite coatings include two advanced structures: gradient coating and in-situ reactive coating [3]. Masyuhi NINO and Shuhei MAED proposed the concept of gradient composite structure [4]. Gradient structure refers to a material in which the elements that make up the material change continuously along a certain dimension, so that the material properties have corresponding gradient changes in space [5]. In nature, the cross-sectional structure of bamboo shows gradient changes and exhibits excellent mechanical properties. Researchers have been influenced by the gradient structure in nature and have developed many new gradient structure processes

[6, 7]. The process mainly includes two types: surface penetration structure and layered structure. Surface penetration is mainly to form a single layer, multi-layer or continuous penetration layer on the metal surface through physical or chemical methods to change the surface properties of the material, such as carburizing process. The layered structure mainly deposits two or more materials layer by layer to obtain a new surface structure with multiple material properties. This article uses WC coating, SKH51 coating and base material 45 steel to form a gradient structure. Since SKH51 has a certain hardness and wear resistance, it can increase the coating thickness and wear resistance. It has a better service life than WC coating and can meet the life requirements of special parts.

Gradient coatings were widely used in a variety of industries. To consider the different functions of each coating property, researchers had studied the surface coatings on metal substrates. Gradient coatings can improve the surface properties such as bond strength, wear resistance, corrosion resistance, surface hardness and heat resistance [8]. M.C. Perju improved the wear resistance of the surface of Fe-C alloy parts by depositing three coatings of Ti/W/WC on the surface [9]. Zhang carried out a study on the composite of three coatings on the surface of tin bronze to improve the wear re-

sistance of the sliding bearings with better wear resistance and reduced total cost by using the friction reducing material B83 [10]. Tarelnyk performed multi-layer deposition of carbon, aluminum and T18K10 hard layers on alloy steel substrates to obtain coating thickness and properties [11]. Zheng and Zhou used Ni/(TiCP/Ni)/Ni to eliminate TiC cracks and thus improve electrode life of spot welding [12]. K.A. Kuptsov used two-layer coatings process to improve the surface properties of titanium alloys [13]. Vladimir used electro-spark alloying and thermal diffusion boriding of steel to enhance the surface wear resistance of steel [14]. Hao deposited TiN/Ti composite coatings on TC4 surface by TA2 electrode [15]. Wu prepared Zr/WC composite coatings on TA2 surface to study the modification of Ti metal surface [16]. One benefit of gradient coatings in the ESD deposition process is that it can combine materials for many different uses. In particular, super hard wear-resistant materials were used to avoid defects caused by excessive increase in coating thickness. Gradient deposition with high toughness materials can improve the impact toughness of the coating itself. It avoided excessive hardness difference with the substrate. With the development of ESD process, people have conducted a lot of experiments in one-layer coated alloy materials. And they found that iron, nickel and cobalt material have better connectivity than the monolithic metal, which can be used as a transition coating. SKH51 is an iron alloy material, which is easier to connect with 45 steel and WC coating. It can be used as a transition coating, has a good impact toughness, which can further improve the stability of the

coating[17, 18]. The SKH51 material itself is an iron alloy material, which is easier to connect with 45 steel and cobalt of WC coating. It can be used as a transition coating to further improve the stability of the coating. It can be used as a transition coating to further improve the stability of the coating. The WC coating is used to further improve the wear resistance of the coating [19]. Then, it was coated with a Babbitt alloy of B83 to further reduce coating friction and thus increase coating life. Meanwhile, B83 material belongs to tin-based alloy, which is more corrosion resistant than cobalt alloy. It will enhance the performance of the coating. With the demand for remanufactured high life parts in industry, the advantages of ESD composite coating have been brought back to the attention of companies.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Material Analysis

SKH51 electrode belongs to the tungsten-molybdenum system of high-carbon high-speed tool steel. The hardness of SKH51 electrode material is 62-65 HRC. The spark electrode is a rod with a diameter of 2.5mm (Jinxin Co., Ltd.), which is made of SKH51 material from Japan, and its composition is as shown in Table 1. WC electrodes are selected 3mm HF10F electrode material from Sandvik Company, which contains 10% cobalt and 90% tungsten carbide (WC); Tungsten carbide particle size is 0.8 microns, and its hardness is HRA92.1 (77HRC), tungsten carbide particle size is 0.8 microns, and its hardness is HRA92.1 (77HRC). The base material is 45 steel with a hardness of 22-32HRC. It was selected the 3mm size of B83 electrode in Table 2.

Table 1

Element of SKH51 Alloy

Element	W	Mo	Cr	V	C	Si	Fe
Content(%)	5.8	4.8	4	1.8	0.85	0.45	other

Table 2

Element of B83 Alloy

Element	Sb	Cu	Sn	other
Content(%)	11	6	other	0.1

2.2 Deposition process and Parameters

Firstly, the size of the 45 steel deposition substrate specimen (length, width and height) was selected as 25mm x 30mm x 2 mm, and the specimens were firstly sanded with 240#, 400#, 800# and 1200# sandpaper to remove the oxidized layer and impurities. The surface to be coated was then cleaned with acetone and alcohol for ultrasonic cleaning. At the same time, a hair dryer was used to dry the surface of the specimens. A type ESD cladding machine was used, which of model was HMT9500 (Shengzao Co., China). The output voltage is AC 220 V, single-phase 50/60 Hz, the input power is 1500W, and the discharge frequency is 500Hz. And 3 specimens were manufactured for each experiment.

2.3 Materials Testing methods

After the sample was deposited, acetone was used for surface scrubbing, and anhydrous alcohol was used for surface ultrasonic cleaning. The surface morphology was observed by a Leica ultra-depth-of-field microscope (LEICA DM6). Bruker D8 was used to analyze the composition of the composite coating by X-ray diffraction (XRD). Thickness measurements were carried out by a coating thickness gauge (Aicevoos, AS-x6). Then, the surface roughness test was measured with a roughness meter (Taiming Optical Co., Ltd., JB-IC). For the tribological performance test, a reciprocating friction and wear machine MWF-500 (Jinan Huaxing Co.) was selected to conduct a wear resistance test

on the coating surface. The powder on the surface of the samples was removed by brushing, wiped by scratching with anhydrous alcohol and dried naturally. The abrasion marks were measured by a Leica Super Depth of Field Microscope DM6 (LEICA Co.,). The toughness of the coating was tested by applying 294.2N (30.0kgf) pressure to the coating with Vickers hardness HVS-50 (Huayin Co., China).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Surface morphology

An ultra-depth-of-field microscope was used to observe the surfaces of SKH51 coating, WC coating, SKH51+WC coating, and SKH51+WC+B83 coating. All three coating surfaces formed white fish-scale melt droplets, and the melt droplets on the surface of SKH51 coating were more uniform, as shown in Fig.1. During the deposition process, because SKH51 has better thermal hardness, deposition surface was rougher, deposition friction was higher, but melt droplet brightness was highest. While WC electrode had less friction and was

very easy to deposit. The surface of the specimen was enlarged to 500X and the coating was found to have flatter metal melt droplets [20]. No large metal cracks were found on the surface of SKH51, but more obvious cracks were found on the surfaces of WC coating, SKH51+WC coating, as shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3 [21]. The droplets on the surface of the SKH51+WC coating are larger than those of the other two coatings. These cracks are thermal stress cracks generated after deposition of the cemented carbide material on the coating surface. The deposition time is longer, the crack distribution on the surface of WC increases and is more affected. From Fig.3, it can be found that the SKH51 coating and WC coating were flatter than the SKH51+WC coating. The surface of SKH51+WC coating was more uneven. Due to the lower melting point of the material, B83 coating had larger metal droplets on the surface and the surface was rough in Fig.4. Since B83 material contained Cu, there was yellow metal deposition on the surface.

Figure 1-Surface morphology of SKH51 coating: a-original morphology; b-500X morphology; c-2D super depth of field image.

Figure 2-Surface morphology of WC Coating: a-original morphology; b-500X morphology; c-2D super depth of field image.

Figure 3-Surface morphology of SKH51+WC Coating: a-original morphology; b-500X morphology; c-2D super depth of field image.

Figure 4-Surface morphology of SKH51+WC+B83 Coating: a-original morphology; b-500X morphology; c-2D super depth of field image.

3.2 XRD analysis

SKH51+WC gradient coating mainly resisted the effects of wear. Therefore, the gradient coating was subjected to XRD analysis of the SKH51+WC composite coating by Bruker D8. It was found that the surface of the WC coating was mainly composed of electrode materials WC, W₂C, Fe₃W₃C, Co, and Fe, as shown in Fig.5 [22, 23]. The appearance of metal-ceramic WC and W₂C materials was the main reason for the surface wear resistance. Between the WC and SKH51 coatings, a small amount of Fe in the SKH51 coating was doped

into the carbide surface coating because of the effect of the rotating electrode of the ESD equipment. The generated Fe₃W₃C is M₆C type carbide which is also able to increase the wear resistance of the surface [24]. Co metal is a binder for cermet [25]. The presence of Fe which can also form a bonding effect. The presence of other compounds components was not clearly observed. The elements MO, Cr, V and their compounds could not be analyzed due to the high diffraction peaks of Fe.

Figure 5-XRD pattern of EDM deposited SKH51+WC coating

3.3 Surface coating thickness

According to the experimental program, three specimens of SKH51 coating were measured and the mean and average variance of the thickness was calculated. Three specimens of WC coating were also measured and the mean and average variance of the thickness was taken. Similarly, the same statistics on the

SKH51+WC coatings and SKH51+WC+B83 coatings were shown in Fig.6, where SKH51+WC+B83 coating was the thickest with an average value of 133.8 μm. The WC coating had the smallest thickness with a thickness of 30.9μm. According to the variance curve, it can be seen that the higher the thickness of the coatings, the higher the standard deviation.

Figure 6-Coating thickness

3.4 Roughness analysis

The roughness of 4 groups of ESD coatings was measured on the surfaces. Using a JB-IC roughness meter, the standard $\lambda_s=0.8$ was selected and the surface was measured in 4.8 mm length. Three measurements were taken on each specimen surface, and the mean and standard deviation of the Ra of the samples were counted and calculated as shown in Fig.7. It was found that the standard deviation of the standard coating thickness increases as the number of layers increases. The quality of every coating has an impact on the next

coating. From the figure, it is observed that the substrate 45 steel has less effect on the coating quality. The SKH51+WC+B83 coating has the maximum value of roughness and the SKH51 coating has the minimum roughness. Among them, the most important in SKH51+WC+B83 was the quality of the transition layer SKH51 coating. Due to the lower melting point of B83, the deposition was affected by the process, and the surface roughness value was the largest.

Figure 7-Coating surface roughness

3.5 Tribological performance analysis

The tribological properties of the coating surface were investigated with a reciprocating friction wear machine MWF-500 (Huaxing Co.), in which the test parameters were selected: load 30N, spindle speed 150r/min, test time 15min, linear test length 6mm. 5mm friction ball (ZrO₂, G10 precision) was used for the surface abrasion test. According to the order of coating deposition, 45 steel substrate, SKH51 coating,

SKH51+WC coating, and SKH51+WC+B83 coating were investigated, and 3 groups of tests were conducted at the same coating. In Fig.8, it can be seen that the friction coefficient of SKH51+WC coating was the largest, SKH51 coating coefficient was the smallest which was 0.07, and the friction coefficient of SKH51+WC coating was effectively reduced by B83 coating from 0.23 to 0.12, which achieved the purpose of friction reduction.

Figure 8-Friction coefficient of coating surface

It can be seen from Figure 9 that even if the surface roughness value of the base 45 steel was very small, the friction force was still large. Due to the properties of SKH51 coating, surface friction was greatly reduced by 67% and had certain wear resistance. The WC coating with good wear resistance was deposited on the SKH51

coating. Because of the surface micro-texture, the friction coefficient first increased and then decreased. However, the friction coefficient increases to 0.23, and the friction force increases by 2 times than SKH51 coating. As a friction-reducing material, B83 coating can reduce the friction coefficient of SKH51+WC coating, reducing friction by 48%.

Figure 9-Surface friction process

As shown in Figure 10, B83 had larger wear marks due to the softer material. Very few wear debris were observed on coating, and it was mainly plastic deformation and polishing wear on wear surface. Since both SKH51 coating and WC coating were wear-resistant materials, the wear marks were smaller. Among them, since the content of WC was higher than that of SKH51, WC coating had better wear resistance. Obvious scratches appeared on the surface of the SKH51 coating and WC coating, which were mainly abrasive wear and a small amount of adhesive wear. As shown in Fig.10, the average width of WC coating was 586.12μm, corresponding to the coating thickness of 17.24μm. The average width of SKH51 coating was 619.22μm, corresponding to the coating thickness of 19.25μm, and the

width of 45 steel was 699.52μm, corresponding to the coating thickness of 24.59μm. Without considering the arc pit wear part at both ends, the wear volume was shown in Table 3. From the perspective of wear volume, the wear resistance of SKH51 coating was 30.7% higher than that of 45 steel. The wear resistance of SKH51+WC coating was 15.3% higher than that of SKH51 coating. Although B83 has large wear marks, there was almost no wear debris. Because the surface was soft, the material undergoes plastic deformation and the material will not be lost. Therefore, the wear volume of the B83 coating was not counted. The soft metal in the coating mainly played the role of reducing friction.

Table 3

Wear scar parameters			
Material	Wear scar width (mm)	Wear scar depth (mm)	Approximate volume of wear scar (mm ³)
45	0.69952	0.02459	0.0688
SKH51	0.61922	0.01925	0.0477
SKH51+WC	0.58612	0.01724	0.0404

Figure 10-Average wear scar on the surface

3.6 Impact toughness

In order to avoid the increase in hardness caused by grinding, HVS-50 Vickers hardness tester was used to select flat areas for testing on the WC coating and SKH51+WC coating. Under the pressure of 30kg (i.e. 294.2N), the tests were conducted separately. It was found that the indenter area of SKH51+WC coating was 0.0424mm², as shown in Fig.11; the indenter area of WC coating was 0.2529 mm². Since both coatings were made of WC material, under small loads, the pressure head areas of the two coatings were not much different. Under the condition of large load pressure, the pressure head area of SKH51+WC coating was much smaller than the pressure head area of WC coating.

SKH51+WC gradient coating can better ensure the performance of WC materials than WC single-layer coating. There was a large hardness difference between the single-layer WC coating and the base 45 steel. 45 steel was soft, with a hardness of 22~32HRC, and the WC coating had a higher hardness of 77HRC, which made it easy to deform and break under large loads. In the SKH51+WC coating, the SKH51 transition coating had certain hardness, with a hardness of 62-65 HRC. The material itself had a certain hardness and impact toughness, which ensured the performance of the WC coating of the SKH51+WC coating under large loads. It can improve the bonding force of the coating and impact toughness in extreme conditions.

Figure 11-Comparison of pressure resistance between gradient coating and single WC coating: a-SKH51+WC coating; b- WC coating.

4 Conclusions

Composite coatings have more functions than single-layer coatings. It has more advantages in improving surface wear resistance, reducing friction and resisting corrosion. Using gradient structures, composite coatings can have better performance. Due to the ESD process, the thickness of the coating is limited. The greater the thickness is, the lower the deposition efficiency is. The composite gradient coating process can increase the coating thickness, improve the wear resistance of the coating, and improve the surface life of the parts. SKH51+WC+B83 composite coating has the best performance in wear resistance.

1) The SKH51+WC+B83 composite coating has good surface wear resistance, anti-friction and anti-corrosion. It is able to meet the extreme surface requirements of industry for repairing worn parts. The performance of SKH51 transition coating is an important factor to enhance the surface of the composite coating. SKH51 material has better adhesion and can replace the traditional nickel alloy transition layer.

2) The gradient structure of SKH51+WC coating provides better impact and wear resistance than WC single-layer coating. Its gradient structure further enhances the wear resistance of the coating.

3) The friction coefficient of SKH51+WC coating is effectively reduced by B83 coating, which reduces the friction of the coating and enhance the coating wear resistance. It further improves the wear resistance of the coating. It has better corrosion resistance than WC coating, which ensure that the surface of parts has a long life under extreme conditions.

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